

The Influence of China on Major Stock Markets

Louangrath, Paul[★]

ABSTRACT

This paper provides a practical means to verify the level of interdependency between major stock markets in the world and that of China. The recent devaluation of RMB and interest rate change in China were used as two exogenous shocks to gauge the response by major stock markets. This study answers the question of whether China's economic policy significantly influences the world's financial markets. If so, to what extent is that influence? The first question is answered by analyzing the index distribution before and after the shock by analyzing distribution probability of the Z score of each market. The sample consists of daily indices from 15 stock markets over a period of 6 months spanning from September 2015 through February 2016. The Shanghai Exchange was used as a proxy for China. The remaining 14 markets were used to correlate with China on the basis of scale drift measurement and trend direction. It was found that outside of China, only SP100 and DOW are significantly influenced by China. All stock indices from the ASEAN and other Asia Pacific countries showed no significant relations with China. Among the three major exchanges in Europe: FTSE100, CAC400 and DAX all showed complete independence from China. We also report a surprise finding that there was significant market integration among the ASEAN stock markets and that the ASEAN market was independent of China. Using SET as a dependent variable, the coefficient of determination for SET against JKSE (Indonesia), KLCI (Malaysia, and PSEi (Philippines) are 0.97, 0.87 and 0.82 with a significant reading of $T = 11.45, 5.22$ and 4.23 respectively.

Keywords: Goodness-of-fit (GOF), linear regression, maximum likelihood estimation (MLE), Monte Carlo method.

JEL Code: C10, C13, C14, C46, E27. G11, G17

CITATION:

Louangrath, Paul (2016). "The Influence of China on Major Stock Markets." *Inter. J. Res. Methodol. Soc. Sci.*, vol. 2, No. 2 (Apr. - Jun. 2016); pp. 77-92. ISSN 2415-0371.

1. INTRODUCTION

The relevance of China to the ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) and the world marketplace could not be ignored. This paper tests the economic ties of China and those in the AEC. We examine a potential regime shift among the stock markets in the AEC as the result of policy

[★] Loangrath, Paul, Bangkok University – International College (BUIC). For email correspondence: Lecturepedia@gmail.com

changes in China. The Shanghai Composite is used as a proxy for China. The following stock exchanges are used as the representative markets for the AEC: JKSE (Indonesia), KLCI (Malaysia), PSEi (Philippines), and SET (Thailand). Other non AEC markets used for comparison study include Heng Seng (Hong Kong), KOSPI (South Korea), NIKKEI225 (Japan) and TWSE (Taiwan). In addition, the study looks to the influence on China's internal policy on the global market place by tracking the change in index movement in the major European markets: CAC40 (France), DAX (Germany), and FTSE (United Kingdom). Non-AEC markets examined in this paper also include the US exchanges: SP500, DOW and NASDAQ.

The last quarter of 2015 saw the implementation of two main policies by the Chinese government that evidences a "regime shift" (Lendvai, 2006). The first policy shift was the announcement of the reduction of the interest rate. This rate reduction was to adjust the strength of the Chinese currency (RMB) in line with the market's valuation. The second policy shift was the adjustment of the valuation of the Chinese currency itself. Major stock markets throughout the world responded to these two "shocks."

Figure 1. Pattern of Interest Rate Change in China

The needs to measure the level of influence of China and market-to-market interdependency in the context of China's "regime shift" motivate this research (Brock & Carpenter, 2006). Moreover, the continued downward trend of China's capital market becomes an internal-downward spiral no longer influences the external markets. To what extent does China influence the global market place remains an unanswered question. This research intends to fill this gap in the literature.

The intended contribution of this research is to make academic research in market-to-market influence more accessible to decision makers and stakeholders dealing with capital markets. This paper rejects time series modeling, such as AR, ARMA, or ARIMA as impracticable, by adopting system analysis under Weibull.

The research question presented by this paper may be stated as: "how much does China influence major stock markets around the world?" More generally, we also aim to provide a general picture of "how major stock markets around the world are influenced by China?" The answers to these questions are valuable to stakeholders, such as policymakers, risk managers, and investment professionals, because these answers provide a short-hand benchmarking for market-to-market of inter-dependency.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Timer Series Modeling for Stock Market Studies

Financial data is treated as time series data. There are two main lines of methodology used for time dependent event analysis. The first approach is time series modeling. This method is commonly

employed in econometrics (Brockwell & Davis, 2002). The second method is the time-to-event modeling which uses system failure and survival functions analyses.

Conventional econometrics relies on autoregressive family of models for sequential time-based event modeling. Time series modeling is a common tool in social science Zissis *et al.* (2015). These time series modeling may be classified into univariate and multivariate models (NIST: Engineering Handbook, 2013). Univariate time series is common; it consists of a family of autoregressive (AR) modeling. The second type of autoregressive model for univariate time series is called the *moving average* (MA) model.

A third approach to time series modeling is called the Box-Jenkins method which combined AR and MA; thus, it is called ARMA (autoregressive moving average) (Box & Jenkins, 1970). ARMA assumes that the time series are stationary. Stationary means that the data series are reverting to its long-run equilibrium, i.e. mean reverting (Makridakis & Hibon, 1995). If there is an external shock, and the effect of the shock is integrated, the shock destroys the original long-run equilibrium. As the result, the time series lose the memory. The series are no longer mean reverting. If the effect of the shock establishes a new mean, it is said that the time series are integrated; thus, ARMA becomes ARIMA (autoregressive integrated moving average).

The second category of time series forecasting model is the multivariate type. The Box-Jenkins form for multivariate time series is called *autoregressive moving average vector* (ARIMAV). In the present case where China is in the middle of capital market crisis, ARIMA's measurement could only verify whether the effects from exchange rate and interest rate policies are integrated into the series; if so, then what? ARIMA does not have the answer. Therefore, ARIMA is not a useful model to forecast or measure between China and major stock markets around the world.

2.2 Limitation of Time Series Modeling

Since autoregressive modeling uses the prior period's observation as the value for its dependent variable and the current observation as the dependent variable, this "autoregressive" tends to produce a false reading of significance and direction of the trend. To illustrate this point, the QQ plot of the time series is used for AR modeling and its corresponding forecast functions for the 6 months running from September 1, 2015 through February 29, 2016 are listed in Table 1. Note that despite negative market performance and mixed performance throughout the 6 months period, AR model consistently produces positive slope and its beta reading always suggests a positive or increasing trend. Contrasted the AR reading with that obtained through Weibull QQ plot, the resulted forecast function for each month is more informative.

Table 1: Shanghai Composite Forecast under Autoregressive Model (AR)

Daily Index Batch <i>Monthly Run*</i>	Autoregressive Modeling Equation $Y_{AR} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X$	Beta $\beta = \frac{1}{b}$	Trend Direction
September 2015	$Y_{AR_1} = 5.60 + 0.30X$	3.33	Increasing
October 2015	$Y_{AR_2} = 3.07 + 0.63X$	1.58	Increasing
November 2015	$Y_{AR_3} = 2.68 + 0.67X$	1.49	Increasing
December 2015	$Y_{AR_4} = 2.59 + 0.68X$	1.47	Increasing
January 2016	$Y_{AR_5} = 1.14 + 0.85X$	1.18	Increasing
February 2016	$Y_{AR_6} = 2.94 + 0.63X$	1.58	Increasing

*Coverage period: September 1, 2015 through February 29, 2016.

The Chinese government introduced shock to the system in October 2015. By the time the system reacted to the shock in October 2015, the Shanghai Composite is on its way out of the shock

phase. From November and December 2015, the Shanghai Composite starts showing a recovery. It started to dip again in January and February 2016. The picture of the market provided by Weibull's approach as shown in Table 2 provides more information than its AR counterpart.

Table 2: Shanghai Composite QQ Plot against Time under Weibul Linear Regression

Daily Index Batch <i>Monthly Run*</i>	Weibull's Linear Equation $Y_{w_i} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X$	Beta $\beta = \frac{1}{b}$	Trend Direction
September 2015	$Y_{w_1} = 8.04 - 0.01X$	(100.00)	Decreasing
October 2015	$Y_{w_2} = 7.85 - 0.48X$	(2.08)	Decreasing
November 2015	$Y_{w_3} = 8.28 + 0.18X$	5.56	Increasing
December 2015	$Y_{w_4} = 8.36 + 0.35X$	2.86	Increasing
January 2016	$Y_{w_5} = 7.97 - 0.05X$	(20.00)	Decreasing
February 2016	$Y_{w_6} = 7.59 - 0.64X$	(1.56)	Decreasing
September 2015	$Y_{w_1} = 8.04 - 0.01X$	(100.00)	Decreasing

*Coverage period: September 1, 2015 through February 29, 2016.

2.3 Alternative Analytical Tools for Stock Market Analysis

This paper proposes alternative tools for time series analysis. These tools include (i) Weibull distribution test for system analysis, and (ii) modified most-likelihood estimation (mMLE) function as a means for goodness of fit (GOF) testing for the model.

The motivation for employing Weibull as a means for system analysis comes from the fact that each stock market is a system that may be affected by external forces. In this case, China's regime shift serves as a proxy external shock to which all major stock markets react. Weibull system analysis allow use to construct a response trend to the shock and conclude whether the trend is moving from the previous long-term equilibrium. This issue is answer by the sign of β . In addition the value of Weibull's η provides the scale of the system response to shock. Weibull statistics could provide a clearer picture to the system response and the potential trend of the response better than what time series regression modeling could provide.

The rationale for applying mMLE comes from the inefficiency of the conventional MLE function. The new mMLE could provide a more efficient estimate and, thus, makes the forecast more valid and reliable. Validity test is a test for accuracy. The proposed mMLE could achieve this accuracy requirement with more than 90% precision.

2.4 Weibull Distribution for System Analysis

The Weibull Distribution is used to obtain the system hazard function (Weibull, 1951). The hazard function is an appropriate tool because stock market indices responding to China's internal regime shift represent system failure and hazard function deals with system failure. In order to evaluate and forecast the system, it is necessary to verify its failure and survival rate. The following steps are used to obtain Weibull predictive function.

Firstly, the time-to-failure is obtained by:

$$F(t) = \frac{(i + 0.30)}{(n + 0.40)} \tag{1}$$

Secondly, from equation (1), the X-array for the QQ-plot is generated by:

$$X_i = \ln \left(\ln \left(\frac{1}{1-F(t)} \right) \right) \quad (2)$$

This X-array is generated via time counts of events in the data set. In the present case, there are eight quarters of NPL rates reported by the Bank of Thailand.

Thirdly, generate the Y-array for the QQ-plot by using the observed NPL values for the eight quarters in each industry as the basis; thus:

$$Y_i = \ln(NPL_i) \quad (3)$$

With known XY-arrays, we could not generate a Weibull linear regression equation for each industry in a form of $Y_w = a + bX + c$ from which the Weibull statistics are calculated. These Weibull statistics include: β , η , R , $h(t)$, and $s(t)$.

From the Weibull linear equation, the Weibull statistics are obtained. These statistics provides information about the underlying condition of the process. Firstly, the *beta* value is calculated by:

$$\beta = \frac{1}{b} \quad (4)$$

If $\beta > 1$, it means that the system failure is increasing with respect to time. If $\beta < 1$, it means that the system failure is decreasing with respect to time. If $\beta = 1$, it means that the system failure is stable.

The second Weibull statistic is *eta*: η which is obtained by:

$$\eta = e^a \quad (5)$$

Eta informs us about the scale of the failure distribution. In the present case, the reading of the NPL data commences quarter 1 of 2013 and ends on quarter 4 of 2014.

The third Weibull statistic that provides failure information is the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF). The CDF value provides the total failure reading in percentage distribution form from the beginning to end of the time interval. This value was obtained by:

$$CDF = 1 - \exp \left(- \frac{X}{\eta} \right)^{1/\beta} \quad (6)$$

The fourth Weibull reading is the system reliability. If the system has a total failure of 0.48 in the entire period, how reliable is the system in producing such a failure? The answer to this question is given by the system reliability: R whose value is determined by: $R = 1 - CDF$.

The last set of Weibull statistics are the instantaneous failure rate: $h(t)$ and the system survival rate: $s(t)$ which are given by:

$$h(t) = \left(\frac{\beta}{\eta^\beta} \right) \left(X^{\beta-1} \right) \exp \left(- \frac{X}{\eta} \right)^\beta \quad (7)$$

The value of $h(t)$ indicates the rate of instantaneous failure of the system. In the present case, $h(t)$ indicates the probability that the NPL would fail at any given time.

3. DATA

The data used in this study is comprised of daily close of major indices from a period of six months from September 2015 through February 2016. Major stock indices used in this research come from the following sources: 9 from Asia, 3 from North America, and 3 from Europe. A total of 14 indices outside of China, and one China’s proxy (Shanghai Composite) are used.

Table 3: Major Stock Markets Tested for Market-to-Market Interdependence

Asia	North America	Europe
Heng Seng (Hong Kong)	SP500 (USA)	DAX (Germany)
JKSE (Indonesia)*	DOW (USA)	CAC40 (France)
KLCI (Malaysia)*	NASDAQ (USA)	FTSE100 (UK)
KOSPI (S. Korea)		
NIKKEI-225 (Japan)		
PSEi (Philippines)*		
SET (Thailand)*		
SHA (Shanghai, China)		
TWD (Taiwan)		

*ASEAN countries. The stock markets in Laos and Vietnam are omitted for lack of volume trading and number of listing.

3.1 Sample Size Determination

The sample size determination was accomplished by two approaches, namely sample calculation for continuous data and discrete data. The continuous data in this research is comprised of time series data of the stock indices from major stock markets. The indices are taken from the daily close. Day-to-day the indices reading may post an increase or decrease. The changes (increase and decrease) are used as discrete data. These discrete are defined by the following definition rule (i) increase = 1 and (ii) decrease = 0, thus creating a categorical data of [1,0] for binomial distribution analysis and sample size determination.

3.2 Continuous Data Sample Size Determination

Continuous data in this research consists of time series data of stock indices from various major stock markets. The minimum sample size determination was accomplished under the Weibull method (Gou *et al.* 2013) outlines three steps in obtaining minimum sample size for time series under the Weibull approach. Step 1, calculate the Weibull scale called *eta* (η) where:

$$\eta = \frac{t}{(-\ln(R_t))^{1/\beta}} \tag{9}$$

Step 2 involves the determination of the reliability of the time series, thus:

$$R(t) = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{T}{\eta} \right)^\beta \right] \tag{10}$$

Step 3 requires the use of $R(t)$ to obtain the sample size:

$$1 - CL = \sum_{i=1}^f \binom{n}{i} (1 - R)^i R^{n-i} \quad (11)$$

According to Gou, the minimum sample size for Weibull's distribution function may be obtained by:

$$1 - CI = R^n \quad (12)$$

where CI = confidence interval; R = Weibull reliability; and n = sample size. The confidence used for sample size determination is 99%. Since $1 - CI = \alpha$, equation (12) may be written as:

$$\alpha = R^n \quad (13)$$

The mean of the Weibull reliability for the study period is $R + SD = 0.51$. Using 0.99 as the confidence interval, the value for alpha is $\alpha = 0.01$. The sample size is $n = 7$. The sample size used in this research is comprised of 60 in-sample and 60 out-of-sample counts or a total of 120 counts of time series events.

3.3 Discrete Data Sample Size Determination

The second class of data found in this research is discrete data which obeys the law of binomial distribution. The daily indices were discretized by defining the positive change as 1 and negative change as 0. In this type of experimental design, the sample size determination is given by:

$$n = \left(\frac{Z_{\alpha/2} \sqrt{p_0(1-p_0)} + \beta \sqrt{p(1-p_0)}}{p - p_0} \right)^2 \quad (14)$$

where ...

$$\beta_{p < p_0} = 1 - \Phi \left(\frac{p_0 - p - Z_{\alpha} \sqrt{p_0(1-p_0)}/m}{\sqrt{p(1-p_0)}/n} \right) \quad (14.1)$$

$$\beta_{p > p_0} = 1 - \Phi \left(\frac{p_0 - p - Z_{\alpha} \sqrt{p_0(1-p_0)}/m}{\sqrt{p(1-p_0)}/n} \right) \quad (14.2)$$

Sample size determination for discrete data is $n \geq 30$ (Agresti, 2002).

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Preliminary Data Distribution Test

Data distribution test is accomplished by Anderson-Darling (AD) (Anderson & Darling, 1952). The rationale is to verify whether the data is normally distributed because most statistical tests require that the data be normally distributed. With known distribution type, appropriate statistical tests could be used. The AD test consists of two steps: first, determine the observed value for AD and second, compare the observed AD value to that of the theoretical value: AD^* . The observed value for AD is obtained through:

$$AD = -n - S \quad (15)$$

where S is defined as:

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{2k-1}{n} \right) [\ln(F(Z)) + \ln(1-F(Z))] \quad (16)$$

The theoretical value for AD^* is given by:

$$AD^* = AD \left(1 + \frac{0.752}{n} + \frac{2.25}{n^2} \right) \quad (17)$$

The decision rule is: $H_0 : AD < AD^*$ assumed that the data is normally distributed and $H_A : AD > AD^*$ that the data is non-normally distributed. The data from the markets are normally distributed because $AD < AD^*$. After the data distribution was verified, the data was tested for randomness.

Data randomness is verified by the adjacent test. The rationale for randomness test comes from the fact that most statistical tests require randomness in the data set. For $n < 25$, the test statistic is given by:

$$L_{n < 25} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (x_{i+1} - x_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \quad (18)$$

The null hypothesis assumes randomness and this assumption may be rejected if the test statistic lies outside the lower and upper bounds of the critical value. The hypothesis statement is: $H_0 : L_{lower} < L_{obs} < L_{upper}$ and the data is non-random if L_{obs} lies outside of the lower and upper boundaries.

Trend test was used to confirm whether market indices manifest any trends: recognizable patterns with magnitude and direction. Trend may be classified as improving or deteriorating trend. The Reverse Arrangement (RA) Test was used to accomplish this task. This is the trend test applicable to daily changes of market indices in the present case. The RA test is given by:

$$Z_{RA} = \frac{R - \left(\frac{r(r-1)}{4} \right) + 0.50}{\sqrt{\frac{(2r-5)(r-1)r}{72}}} \quad (19)$$

where R is the reverse counts, and r is the number of repair time or sample size. A reverse count R is the number of time that the sign changes from + to – among the observations. The market indices are tested under the RA test to verify whether significant trend exists.

4.2 Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing was accomplished in three phases: (i) system analysis was accomplished by Weibull distribution test, (ii) data outlier test was accomplished under GEV, and (iii) forecast model testing was accomplished under mMLE with the aid of Monte Carlo simulation.

System analysis under Weibull allows us to verify the moving trend of each stock market. These directional trends could be compared to the movement of China’s internal market. This comparison study could point to the level of inter-dependence between major stock indices and China’s internal development.

mMLE and Monte Carlo simulation helps to verify the reliability of the model via asymptotic normality under the simulation process. If the proposed model is reliable and accurate, the expected error would be small and the simulation counts would also be smaller in order to obtain the necessary distribution normality. The standard used for the Monte Carlo simulation is 0.998 or 3σ units.

4.3 Log-Likelihood Function Testing to Verify Proposed Model

This paper proposes to modify the log likelihood function in order to reduce the bias or inaccuracy between the arithmetic mean and the expected value. The proposed function consists of two steps: (i) determine the log likelihood of $(X_i : x_1, \dots, x_n)$ under the mMLE, and (ii) adjust the estimate the mMLE in (i) by subtracting $(\ln L(X))^{-n-1}$. The proposed log-likelihood in step 1 is given by:

$$\ln L(Y) = \sum \left(\frac{X_i \ln F(Z)}{n-1} \right) + \left(\frac{(1-X_i)(1-F(Z))}{n^2-n-1} \right) \tag{20.1}$$

where X_i = observations; $Z = (X_i - \bar{X})/S$; $F(Z)$ = percentage probability provided in the Z table corresponding to the value of each Z ; and n = sample size. This new likelihood function is an estimation tool for model testing. It is a modification of the conventional maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) function. The second step of mMLE involves the estimation of the expected value of the series:

$$E[Y] = \frac{1}{n} \sum (Y_i - \ln L(Y)) - \left| \frac{1}{n} \sum \ln L(Y_i) \right| \tag{20.2}$$

Conventional MLE is given by:

$$\ln L(X) = \frac{1}{n} \sum (X_i \ln L(F(Z)) + (1-X_i) \ln L(1-F(Z))) \tag{21}$$

This old MLE is not efficient because its power for estimation is low due to inaccuracy when the sample size is small. In financial analysis, especially financial crisis where the data comes from a situation with crisis in the making, old MLE performs poorly by either over or under estimate the forecast value.

5. FINDINGS & DISCUSSION

Data trend was accomplished by the Adjacent Test where less of 25 observations were used. Random is found is the empirical L value lies between $1.37 < L < 2.63$. In this study, many markets fail to meet this requirement. It tells us that market movement is more predictable than being completely random. If the market reflects human behavior, it would make sense to see that in some circumstances the market indices are not completely random since it reflects investors’ behavior and investors behavior may follow predictable patterns.

A random test was conducted for all markets. Most statistical tests required that the data be random. In the present case, regression model is used. Regression modeling requires that all data

sets are random. For purposes of random test, monthly data for each market is used. It was found that all markets manifest $Z_{RA} < -6.00$ which is much less than the required threshold of 1.65.

5.1 China Market Influence on Global Capital Markets

As Shanghai Composite is used as a proxy for China, we estimate the expected value for the intercept of the Weibull regression as the log-scale of the market. The observed mean for the 6 months is 7.99. Using our modified maximum likelihood estimation (mMLE) function (Steps 1 & 2) and its application for market-to-market associated risk (Step 3):

$$\text{Step 1: } \ln L(Y) = \sum \left(\frac{X_i \ln F(Z)}{n-1} \right) + \left(\frac{(1-X_i)(1-F(Z))}{n^2-n-1} \right)$$

$$\text{Step 2: } E[Y] = \frac{1}{n} \sum (Y_i - \ln L(Y)) - \left| \frac{1}{n} \sum \ln L(Y_i) \right|$$

$$\text{Step 3: } E[Y]R^2$$

where R^2 is the coefficient of determination obtained through market-to-market linear regression under Weibull's QQ plot.

It was found that the estimated value of $E[Y] = 7.65$. This finding reveals that the Shanghai Composite is expected to drop 7.99 to 7.65 in the near future; this is an expected drop of 0.34 point. Where the observed standard deviation is 0.30, using the standard score to verify the significance level of the difference between the expected and observed mean, the score is -1.13 (12.51%) compared to 1.65 (95%) of the null hypothesis.

The downward pressure of the Shanghai Composite may be verified by the Monte Carlo Simulation method. Using a target percentage confidence of 99.87%, a random generating numbers could be generated with 22,500 iterations to obtain the expected mean of $\hat{\mu}_{SHA} = 7.31 \pm 0.39$. According to Monte Carlo simulation, the expected mean of the scale for Shanghai Composite is between 6.92 and 7.70. Thus, our estimation of 7.65 is in agreement with the simulation. Both under the mMLE estimation and conventional Monte Carlo simulation points to a downward pressure. *See Appendix 1*

Among the global market place, there are two markets that proved to be significantly influenced by China: SP500 and DOW. By multiplying the coefficient of determination between Shanghai Composite and the SP500 and DOW by the prospect of downside risk, we could obtain the expected fall or rise in SP500 and DOW. The r-squared score for SP500 vis-à-vis Shanghai Composite is 0.60; thus, the expected short fall in the SP500 is 0.0751 or 7.51% and for DOW with R-squared value of 0.46, the prospective market short fall is 0.0575 or 5.75% with respect to continuing financial crisis in China.

The scale of indices of SP500 and DOW could also be subjected to Monte Carlo simulation in order to verify whether the estimated downward pressure above is reliable. It was found that with 22,500 iterations, the expected mean for SP500 is $\hat{\mu}_{SP500} = 0.70 \pm 1.49$ and for DOW is $\hat{\mu}_{DOW} = 0.72 \pm 1.46$. Under simulation, both SP500 and DOW were underperformed. This number appears unrealistic; thus, in this case the Monte Carlo simulation method, despite its widespread use and specified confidence interval of 99.87% and 22,500 iterations, has reliability less than the proposed mMLE function.

Similar estimation could also be accomplished for the stock markets in the AEC and Asia Pacific (non-ASEAN); however, this prospect is foreclosed by the fact that these markets are not significantly influenced by China, except Heng Seng (Hong Kong). The Heng Seng index correlates China by 0.61 R-squared level; this translates into $0.61(0.1251) = 0.0763$ or 7.63% market short fall if China continues to experience financial market crisis. This market-to-market interdependence

measurement is accomplished by: $E[Y]R^2$ where $E[Y]$ is the mMLE value and R^2 is the coefficient of determination between the subject markets, i.e. China and its target associated market.

5.2 China's Influence on Stock Markets in the US

The finding shows that the Shanghai Composite has a cycle movement between positive and negative slope for the past six months. In the past six months, the Shanghai Composite shows negative slope for two months and positive for two months. This is a two months cycle. The significance of the upside is $p = (s + 1)/(n + 2) = 0.375$ (LaPlace, 1841) and $q = 0.625$. The significance test under the DeMoivre-Laplace theorem follows:

$$Z = \frac{X_n - np}{\sqrt{npq}} = \frac{2 - 6(0.375)}{\sqrt{6(0.375)(0.625)}} = \frac{2 - 2.25}{\sqrt{1.40}} = \frac{-0.25}{1.06} = -0.23 \rightarrow F(Z) = 0.4013$$

China's proxy (Shanghai Composite) shows an upside risk of 40.13% or there is a probability of market moving in a negative direction of 59.87%. The prospect of the upside is statistically not significant.

Table 4. Comparison of China to North America Stock Markets

Shanghai	SP500	DOW	NASDAQ
$Y_{w_1} = 8.04 - 0.01X$	$Y_{w_1} = 4.76 - 0.05X$	$Y_{w_1} = 4.71 - 0.04X$	$Y_{w_1} = 4.71 - 0.04X$
$Y_{w_2} = 7.85 - 0.48X$	$Y_{w_2} = 4.49 - 0.06X$	$Y_{w_2} = 4.49 - 0.06X$	$Y_{w_2} = 4.49 - 0.06X$
$Y_{w_3} = 8.28 + 0.18X$	$Y_{w_3} = 4.23 - 0.07X$	$Y_{w_3} = 4.23 - 0.07X$	$Y_{w_3} = 4.23 - 0.07X$
$Y_{w_4} = 8.36 + 0.35X$	$Y_{w_4} = 3.98 + 0.13X$	$Y_{w_4} = 3.86 - 0.11X$	$Y_{w_4} = 3.86 - 0.11X$
$Y_{w_5} = 7.97 - 0.05X$	$Y_{w_5} = 3.29 - 0.15X$	$Y_{w_5} = 3.30 - 0.16X$	$Y_{w_5} = 3.30 - 0.16X$
$Y_{w_6} = 7.59 - 0.64X$	$Y_{w_6} = 1.79 - 0.60X$	$Y_{w_6} = 1.79 - 0.06X$	$Y_{w_6} = 1.79 - 0.06X$

Periods: T1 = September 2015; T2 = October 2015; T3 = November 2015; T4 = December; T5 = January 2016; and T6 = February 2016.

The intercept or scales of the markets are subjected to correlation coefficient determination by using Shanghai Composite as the proxy against which other markets are correlated. It was determined that the mean correlation coefficient for SP500, DOW and NASDAQ to Shanghai Composite is $\bar{r}_{US} = 0.63 \pm 0.01$, the test for significance under $T_r = (\bar{r}\sqrt{n-2})/\sqrt{1-\bar{r}^2}$ is only 0.81 compare to the null hypothesis' of $T_{r,*} = 1.64$ for 95% confidence interval. It is concluded that China does not have significant effect on the scale of the market in the US.

The next issue is the comparison of the slope. The slope series for six months of Shanghai Composite is used as the explanatory variable (independent variable X) to explain the dependent variable Y (individual US stock market index: SP500, DOW and NASDAQ). It was found that for the SP500, the relation is $Y_{\beta_1} = -0.06 + 0.52X$ with a significance level of $T = 2.56$ compared to the theoretical value of 1.64. This comparison for SP500 has a coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.60$. In terms of direction of the market, SP500 is influenced by China by 60% and that influence is statistically significant with T-reading exceeding 95% confidence interval.

The second slope comparison for the US market is the DOW. The DOW index shows a directional relationship with Shanghai Composite of $Y_{\beta_2} = -0.14 - 0.32X$ having a significance reading o 1.86 and $R^2 = 0.46$ where as NASDAQ (a technology stock issues of the US markets) is

not influenced by China. The NASDAQ’s Weibull slope relationship with Shanghai Composite is $Y_{\beta 3} = -0.09 - 0.04X$ with a significance reading of $T = 0.73$ and $R^2 = 0.12$.

These findings have significant and practical implications. Despite speculations that China’s “regime shift” causes the global market to react negatively, empirical tests in this study show that the effect is mixed in the US. The scale analysis shows that the effect of China does not significantly cause drifting of the intercept (index scale) the US stock indices. However, China influences the direction or market trend direction of SP500 and DOW significantly.

5.3 China’s Influence on Stock Markets in Europe

We find similar pattern in slope analysis. For scale analysis, it is found that $\bar{r}_{EU} = 0.62 \pm 0.01$ with the observed value of significance test of $T_{r(EU)} = 0.80$. China has no significant influence on the European stock markets. Similar pattern is found in the slope of the Weibull regression for the European market. The FTSE100, CAC40 and DAX like their US counter-parts (SP500, DOW and NASDAQ) are consistently negative.

Table 5. Comparison of China to European Markets

Shanghai	FTSE100	CAC40	DAX
$Y_{w_1} = 8.04 - 0.01X$	$Y_{w_1} = 4.73 - 0.05X$	$Y_{w_1} = 4.74 - 0.05X$	$Y_{w_1} = 4.72 - 0.05X$
$Y_{w_2} = 7.85 - 0.48X$	$Y_{w_2} = 4.52 - 0.06X$	$Y_{w_2} = 4.53 - 0.06X$	$Y_{w_2} = 4.50 - 0.06X$
$Y_{w_3} = 8.28 + 0.18X$	$Y_{w_3} = 4.25 - 0.07X$	$Y_{w_3} = 4.26 - 0.07X$	$Y_{w_3} = 4.19 - 0.15X$
$Y_{w_4} = 8.36 + 0.35X$	$Y_{w_4} = 3.95 + 0.012X$	$Y_{w_4} = 3.87 - 0.19X$	$Y_{w_4} = 3.88 - 0.09X$
$Y_{w_5} = 7.97 - 0.05X$	$Y_{w_5} = 3.35 - 0.16X$	$Y_{w_5} = 3.35 - 0.16X$	$Y_{w_5} = 3.35 - 0.16X$
$Y_{w_6} = 7.59 - 0.64X$	$Y_{w_6} = 1.83 - 0.06X$	$Y_{w_6} = 1.83 - 0.16X$	$Y_{w_6} = 1.83 - 0.06X$

A second tier of the analysis looks at the slope regression. The slope series of Shanghai Composite is used as X and those of the FTSE100, CAC400 and DAX were individually used as X. The result shows that: (i) FTSE100 of the UK shows a relationship with China as $Y_{\beta eu1} = -0.06 + 0.03X$ and a significance level of $T = 0.50$ which is less than the theoretical value of 1.64. The coefficient of determination for FTSE100 is $R^2 = 0.05$; (ii) CAC40 of France shows a relationship with Shanghai under slope regression of $Y_{\beta eu2} = -0.11 - 0.06X$ with a significance level of $T = 0.89$ and coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.17$; and (iii) DAX of Germany shows a relationship with China as $Y_{\beta eu3} = -0.10 + 0.06X$ with a significance level of $T = 1.07$ and coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.22$. China has no significant influence on European stock markets.

5.4 China’s Influence on Stock Markets in ASEAN Markets

Similar scale relationship study was carried out with the ASEAN markets and China. It was found that the mean correlation coefficient as a measure of inter-market relationship intensity is $\bar{r}_{ASEAN} = 0.63$ with a significance level of 1.14 compared to the theoretical value of 1.64 for 95% confidence interval. This finding tells us that the influence of China is not large enough to be determinative on market scale drift.

Table 6A. Comparison of China to ASEAN

Shanghai	JKSE	KLCI
$Y_{w_1} = 8.04 - 0.01X$	$Y_{w_1} = 4.64 - 0.13X$	$Y_{w_1} = 4.58 - 0.22X$
$Y_{w_2} = 7.85 - 0.48X$	$Y_{w_2} = 4.43 - 0.14X$	$Y_{w_2} = 4.42 - 0.14X$
$Y_{w_3} = 8.28 + 0.18X$	$Y_{w_3} = 4.16 - 0.15X$	$Y_{w_3} = 4.11 - 0.23X$
$Y_{w_4} = 8.36 + 0.35X$	$Y_{w_4} = 3.74 - 0.31X$	$Y_{w_4} = 3.79 - 0.18X$
$Y_{w_5} = 7.97 - 0.05X$	$Y_{w_5} = 3.24 - 0.28X$	$Y_{w_5} = 3.17 - 0.29X$
$Y_{w_6} = 7.59 - 0.64X$	$Y_{w_6} = 1.75 - 0.67X$	$Y_{w_6} = 1.63 - 0.72X$

Table 6B. Comparison of China to ASEAN

Shanghai	PSEi	SET
$Y_{w_1} = 8.04 - 0.01X$	$Y_{w_1} = 4.62 - 0.13X$	$Y_{w_1} = 4.70 - 0.05X$
$Y_{w_2} = 7.85 - 0.48X$	$Y_{w_2} = 4.41 - 0.06X$	$Y_{w_2} = 4.44 - 0.14X$
$Y_{w_3} = 8.28 + 0.18X$	$Y_{w_3} = 4.01 - 0.37X$	$Y_{w_3} = 4.80 - 0.15X$
$Y_{w_4} = 8.36 + 0.35X$	$Y_{w_4} = 3.72 - 0.31X$	$Y_{w_4} = 3.78 - 0.24X$
$Y_{w_5} = 7.97 - 0.05X$	$Y_{w_5} = 3.20 - 0.38X$	$Y_{w_5} = 3.24 - 0.28X$
$Y_{w_6} = 7.59 - 0.64X$	$Y_{w_6} = 1.69 - 0.70X$	$Y_{w_6} = 1.75 - 0.67X$

A second tier of analysis involved the study of the market trend via the slope analysis. At this point, the slope series of the Shanghai Composite is used as the independent variable X and is regressed as other ASEAN markets (X_s). It was found that Indonesia's market trend relationship with China is $Y_{\beta(JKSE)} = -0.25 + 0.27X$ with a statistical significance level of 1.14 and coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.25$. For Malaysia, the finding shows $Y_{\beta(KLCI)} = -0.26 + 0.34X$ with a statistical significance level of 1.54 and coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.37$. For the Philippines, the finding shows $Y_{\beta(PSEi)} = -0.31 + 0.16X$ with a statistical significance level of 0.56 and coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.07$. Lastly, for Thailand, the finding shows $Y_{\beta(SET)} = -0.22 + 0.33X$ with a statistical significance level of 1.38 and coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.32$. These empirical evidence shows that China does not have significant influence on the market scale or trend direction of stock markets in the ASEAN (AEC).

Among the ASEAN market, there appear to be market interdependence among the ASEAN countries than between ASEAN and China. When SET (Thailand) is regressed against other ASEAN markets it was found that Thailand is significantly influenced by Indonesia, Malaysia and Philippines. This result is shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Evidence of ASEAN Market Integration

Inter-Regional Markets SET as Y	Relationship Function	Significance Level	Coefficient of Determination R^2
SET vs. JKSE	$Y = 0.38 + 1.04X$	11.45	0.97
SET vs. KLCI	$Y = 0.03 + 0.96X$	5.22	0.87
SET vs. PSEi	$Y = 0.03 - 0.88X$	4.23	0.82

5.5 China's Influence on Stock Markets in non-ASEAN Markets

The relationships between China and non-ASEAN markets in Asia Pacific region are compared. The comparison studies looked at the scale and slope of the relationship between markets. The Shanghai Composite index is used as the proxy for China. Other Asia Pacific markets are regression against Shanghai Composite. The summary of the basis for the scale and slope analyses appear in table 9.

Table 8A. Comparison of China to Non-ASEAN Asia Pacific

Shanghai	Heng Seng	KOSPI
$Y_{w1} = 8.04 - 0.01X$	$Y_{w1} = 4.59 - 0.22X$	$Y_{w1} = 4.59 - 0.22X$
$Y_{w2} = 7.85 - 0.48X$	$Y_{w2} = 4.39 - 0.22X$	$Y_{w2} = 4.47 - 0.06X$
$Y_{w3} = 8.28 + 0.18X$	$Y_{w3} = 4.18 - 0.15X$	$Y_{w3} = 4.11 - 0.23X$
$Y_{w4} = 8.36 + 0.35X$	$Y_{w4} = 3.83 - 0.11X$	$Y_{w4} = 3.79 - 0.18X$
$Y_{w5} = 7.97 - 0.05X$	$Y_{w5} = 3.17 - 0.29X$	$Y_{w5} = 3.17 - 0.29X$
$Y_{w6} = 7.59 - 0.64X$	$Y_{w6} = 1.63 - 0.72X$	$Y_{w6} = 1.63 - 0.70X$

Table 8B. Comparison of China to Non-ASEAN Asia Pacific

Shanghai	NIKKEI225	TWSE
$Y_{w1} = 8.04 - 0.01X$	$Y_{w1} = 4.54 - 0.30X$	$Y_{w1} = 4.58 - 0.22X$
$Y_{w2} = 7.85 - 0.48X$	$Y_{w2} = 4.42 - 0.14X$	$Y_{w2} = 4.41 - 0.14X$
$Y_{w3} = 8.28 + 0.18X$	$Y_{w3} = 4.08 - 0.30X$	$Y_{w3} = 4.13 - 0.15X$
$Y_{w4} = 8.36 + 0.35X$	$Y_{w4} = 3.81 - 0.17X$	$Y_{w4} = 3.79 - 0.05X$
$Y_{w5} = 7.97 - 0.05X$	$Y_{w5} = 3.20 - 0.34X$	$Y_{w5} = 2.99 - 0.27X$
$Y_{w6} = 7.59 - 0.64X$	$Y_{w6} = 1.75 - 0.67X$	$Y_{w6} = 0.28 - 0.11X$

It was found that the mean correlation coefficient as a measure of inter-market relationship intensity is $\bar{r}_{AP} = 0.64 \pm 0.02$ with a significance level of 1.17 compared to the theoretical value of 1.64 for 95% confidence interval. This finding tells us that the influence of China is not large enough to be determinative on market scale drift in Asia Pacific.

The last step is to analyze the relationship between China's market trend and those of the Asia Pacific markets. It was found that China has a significant influence on Heng Seng market: $Y_{\beta AP} = -0.24 + 0.46X$ showing a significant level of $T = 2.54$ and coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.61$. The other three markets, KOSPI (S. Korea), NIKKEI225 (Japan), and TAWSE (Taiwan) have no significant relationship with China's market trend. KOSPI's movement vis-à-vis China is $Y_{\beta AP} = -0.25 + 0.28X$ with a T value of 1.14 and $R^2 = 0.25$; and NIKKEI225's movement vis-à-vis China is $Y_{\beta AP} = -0.29 + 0.27X$ with a T value of 1.28 and $R^2 = 0.28$. Lastly, for KWSE the market movement vis-à-vis China is $Y_{\beta AP} = -0.16 + 0.008X$ with a T value of 0.08 and $R^2 = 0.0014$.

5.6 Contribution to the Field

Several lessons are learned from this research: (i) China has no influence on European market; (ii) China influences SP500 and DOW, but not NASDAQ in the US markets; (iii) China has no influence in the ASEAN markets; and (iv) for non-ASEAN Asia Pacific markets, only Heng Seng

Index (Hong Kong) is influenced by China. Other markets such as South Korea, Japan and Taiwan are not influenced by China.

There is an inter-dependence of capital markets among ASEAN countries. This evidence shows that ASEAN, as an economic community (AEC) is more integrated than otherwise believed. The stock indices are more inter-dependent within the AEC markets than with markets outside of the community. This shows that the economic community shows a sign of market integration by moving in the same direction.

6. CONCLUSION

China is known for its size and economic clout in the world market place. One simple question was posed by this research: “Does China influence the world market place? If so, how much influence does China have?” Indices from major stock markets were used to answer this question. It was found that for the most part China does not have influence in the global market place. Particularly, in Asia China has little no influence at all. Among the stock markets in the AEC and non-ASEAN markets in the Asia Pacific, it was found that China does not hold a significant influence on the market scale nor the direction of the market trend. In the global market place, China seems to have a significant influence on two stock indices in the US, namely SP500 and DOW which are expected to experience a market short fall of 7.51% and 5.75% respectively. This information is useful for stakeholders for purposes of risk management and market forecasting.

REFERENCES

- Agresti, Alan (2002). *Categorical Data Analysis*, (2nd ed.). Wiley. p. 232. ISBN 0471360937.
- Anderson, T.W. and Darling, D.A. (1954). “A Test of Goodness-of-Fit.” *Journal of the American Statistical Association*. **49**: 765–769.
DOI: 10.1080/01621459.1954.10501232
<http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/01621459.1954.10501232>
- Anderson, T. W.; Darling, D. A. (1952). “Asymptotic theory of certain ‘goodness-of-fit’ criteria based on stochastic processes.” *Annals of Mathematical Statistics* **23**: 193–212.
DOI:10.1214/aoms/1177729437
<http://projecteuclid.org/euclid.aoms/1177729437>
- Brock, W. A., and S. R. Carpenter (2006). “Variance as a leading indicator of regime shift in ecosystem services.” *Ecology and Society* **11**(2): 9. [online] URL: <http://www.ecologyandsociety.org/vol11/iss2/art9/>
- Brockwell, P.J. and Davis, R.A. (2002). “Introduction to Time Series and Forecasting.” 2nd ed., Springer. ISBN 0-387-95351-5; pp. 6, 38, 59, 60 and 124.
- Guo, Huairui, Pohl, Edward and Gerokostopoulos, Athanasios (2013). “Determining the Right Sample Size for Your Test: Theory and Application,” *2013 Reliability and Maintainability Symposium*, TUTORIAL NOTE, January, 2013; pp. 1-9.
- Laplace, Pierre-Simon (1814). *Essai philosophique sur les probabilités*. Paris: Courcier.
<https://archive.org/details/essaiphilosophiq00lapluoft>
See also Laplace, Pierre Simon, *A Philosophical Essay on Probabilities*, translated from the 6th French edition by Frederick Wilson Truscott and Frederick Lincoln Emory. New York: John Wiley & Sons, 1902, p. 19. Dover Publications edition (New York, 1951) has same pagination.
- Lendvai, J. (2006). “Inflation dynamics and regime shifts.” *European Central Bank, Working Paper Series*, No. 684 / Oct. 2006. Available at <http://www.ecb.int> or from the Social Science Research Network at http://ssrn.com/abstract_id=936638
- Makridakis, S. Hibon, M. (1995). “ARMA Models and the Box-Jenkins Methodology.” INSEAD, 95/45/TM, pp. 1-17.
- NIST (2013). *Engineering Statistics Handbook*, sect. 8.2.3.4, online edition. Accessed: May 12, 2015. <http://www.itl.nist.gov/div898/handbook/apr/section2/apr234.htm>

Weibull, W. (1951), “A statistical distribution function of wide applicability.” *J. Appl. Mech.-Trans. ASME* **18** (3): 293–297.
 Zissis, Dimitrios; Xidias, Elias; Lekkas, Dimitrios (2015). “Real-time vessel behavior prediction.” *Evolving Systems*: 1–12. doi:10.1007/s12530-015-9133-5.

APPENDIX 1 Monte Carlo Simulation

The Monte Carlo simulation may be accomplished by following the procedures outlined below.

1. Rank data to verify the maximum and minimum points among the elements of the set $X_i : (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ such that $X_i \rightarrow X_{(i)}$ from low to high or from high to low. Locate the maximum and minimum value.
2. Use the maxima and minima to estimate the value of E^* where:

$$E^* = \left(\frac{\max - \min}{2} \right) / 50 \tag{A1.1}$$

3. Construct a new data series to create $Y_i : (y_1, y_2, y_3)$ where each element of Y_i is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} y_1 &= \max \\ y_2 &= \min \\ y_3 &= \frac{\max + \min}{2} \end{aligned}$$

4. Find the descriptive and inferential statistics of Y_i where

$$\text{Mean} = \bar{Y} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \tag{A1.2}$$

$$\text{Standard deviation} = S_y = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{Y})^2} \tag{A1.3}$$

$$\text{Estimated mean} = \mu = \bar{Y} - T \left(\frac{S_y}{\sqrt{n}} \right) \tag{A1.4}$$

$$\text{Estimated standard deviation} = \sigma = \left(\frac{\bar{Y} - \mu}{Z} \right) \sqrt{n} \tag{A1.5}$$

5. determine the iteration counts:

$$N = \left(\frac{3\sigma_{y_i}}{E^*} \right)^2 \tag{A1.6}$$